

Towards Automated Insect Farming: Detection and Segmentation of Mealworm Beetles, *Tenebrio molitor*, using Synthetic and Real Datasets

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Abstract

Insects such as mealworms (*Tenebrio molitor*) provide a sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional animal feed sources like soybean and fishmeal. However, rearing insects for mass production is at a very early stage. Therefore, insect farming could benefit from automated solutions that reduce costs and improve scalability and yield. Machine vision can be utilized for remote monitoring and analysis. However, machine vision models are data-hungry as they need a considerable amount of imagery data for model training. Insect farming currently lacks any such dataset. This paper presents synthetic data generated for detecting adult mealworm beetles. Furthermore, a You Only Look Once (YOLO) model trained on synthetic and real farm data is used to identify and count mealworm beetles. Performance using a YOLO model as a benchmark is compared with various patch-based and windowing techniques with varying insect densities. The best model shows an F1 score of 98% in detecting mealworm beetles for a real farm dataset. The paper presents the most

comprehensive analysis of mealworm beetle detection and counting to date. The presented detection results had been demonstrated to produce more reliable and accurate mask predictions, facilitating the preparation of high-quality segmentation datasets. These datasets can serve as a foundation for further vision-based analyses, including size-based classification and anomaly detection.

Keywords: Machine-vision, mealworm farming, counting, YOLO

1 Introduction

The global population has increased significantly, rising from 2.5 billion in 1950 to 8 billion in 2022, with projections estimating a further increase to 9.7 billion by 2050 (United Nations, 2022). This rapid population growth necessitates a corresponding expansion in food production to mitigate food insecurity. While technological advancements have enhanced the quality and quantity of production across various food industries, including livestock and horticulture, sustainable alternatives must be explored to ensure long-term viability. Animal protein, a key dietary component, requires sustainable feed sources. However, the large-scale production of soybean and fishmeal—both primary sources of animal feed—has been linked to deforestation and biodiversity loss (Song et al., 2021), underscoring the need for environmentally friendly and sustainable alternatives (Gasco et al., 2020). Recognizing this challenge, the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) published a report in 2013 highlighting the potential of insects as an alternative food and feed source (Van Huis et al., 2013). The report noted that edible insects have long been part of human diets and that their mass rearing could contribute to global food security.

For large-scale production, insects are typically reared in stacked trays or containers within controlled environments where temperature and humidity are maintained between 20–35°C and 55–75%, respectively (Cadinu et al., 2020). Automation in insect farming has the potential to significantly reduce losses and labour costs by enabling remote monitoring, automated feeding, environmental control, and early detection of diseases caused by viruses and fungi (Cadinu et al., 2020; Hawkey et al., 2021; Niyonsaba et al., 2021; Ibitoye et al., 2025).

Automated insect detection in an insect farming setup can support tasks such as instance segmentation and size-based classification. However, the

automated detection, counting, and sizing of insects remain underexplored due to the lack of sufficiently large and publicly available datasets for training and evaluating machine vision models. To address this gap, this study presents a synthetically generated dataset designed for mealworm beetle detection. Furthermore, it evaluates the performance of a state-of-the-art object detection model, You Only Look Once (YOLO), and presents results based on real-world farm data. Additionally, it demonstrates that the presented detection results improve segmentation.

1.1 Related Work

In recent years, insect farming has gained increasing attention due to its potential to address global food security—one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century. Following the FAO’s report on edible insects (Van Huis et al., 2013), considerable research has been conducted on optimizing insect farming techniques. However, the scalability and efficiency of insect farming relies on automation, particularly through machine vision technologies, which can enhance yield while reducing costs (Nawoya et al., 2024; Ibitoye et al., 2025). The following section summarizes key research efforts related to insect detection and segmentation.

Hansen et al. (2022) developed a low-cost IoT-based system, Insecto, which captures high-resolution images along with environmental data such as temperature, humidity, CO₂ levels, air pressure, and volatile organic compound concentrations. The collected image data was used to count and sex crickets. Using YOLOv5, the cricket counting model achieved an F1 score of 86%, while the VGG-16 model, coupled with an SVM classifier, attained an F1 score of 93% for sex classification. While these results highlight the potential of machine vision in insect counting, the dataset used contained only a limited number of insects per image. As a result, the model’s effectiveness in processing images with higher insect densities remains untested. Majewski et al. (2022) introduced a monitoring system for *Tenebrio molitor* and generated synthetic data to facilitate the annotation process. Their system, utilizing the Mask R-CNN model for instance segmentation, achieved an F1 score of approximately 0.88. The model successfully detected different life stages of mealworms, including larvae, pupae, and adult beetles. However, the dataset used for training and evaluation contained only 3,627 mealworms across the training set and 753 in the test set. Given the total dataset size, the number of mealworms per image was likely low, limiting

the model’s applicability to real-world farming scenarios where insect densities are significantly higher.

Papadopoulos et al. (2024) introduced TenebrioVision, a publicly available, fully annotated dataset for detecting and segmenting *Tenebrio molitor* larvae. The dataset consists of 1,120 images containing 53,600 mealworm instances, divided into training, validation, and test sets in a 75:15:10 ratio. Annotations, including bounding boxes and segmentation masks, were manually created using Dataloader, requiring over 373 hours of effort. The dataset was evaluated using five state-of-the-art object detection and instance segmentation models. YOLOv8 (Instance Segmentation) achieved a mask mAP of 0.729, while YOLO-NAS achieved a bounding box mAP of 0.892, demonstrating superior performance. However, when tested on real-world images, the models struggled with detection accuracy. Data augmentation techniques—such as horizontal and vertical flipping, random rotations, noise addition, zooming, and brightness/exposure adjustments—improved detection performance, sometimes surpassing human-level accuracy. Nevertheless, the dataset contained a maximum of 100 mealworms per image, which may limit its applicability in commercial farming environments where insect densities are substantially higher.

Zhang et al. (2024) proposed a multi-species distribution matching approach (MS-DM) based on density map estimation for counting insects in greenhouses. The method was tested on *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (whiteflies) and *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit flies) and compared with object detection models such as YOLOv5-s, Faster R-CNN, CenterNet, YOLOX-s, and Detection Transformer (DETR). MS-DM demonstrated superior performance in insect counting. However, the method was designed solely for counting and did not support object localization through bounding boxes, making it unsuitable for more advanced tasks such as segmentation or anomaly detection.

Yang et al. (2024) introduced SRNet-YOLO, a novel object detection model that integrates super-resolution reconstruction with feature fusion techniques. Built upon the YOLOv8 backbone, the model incorporates FM-SR and BiformerAF modules to enhance feature extraction. Experimental evaluations showed that SRNet-YOLO outperformed existing models, including YOLOv3, YOLOv5, YOLOv7, YOLOv8, and YOLOv9, particularly in detecting “tiny pests” and “very tiny pests.” The model achieved a mean average precision (mAP) of 92.4% for “tiny pests,” surpassing the second-best performing YOLOv9 model by approximately 9%, and a mAP

of 57% for "very tiny pests," a 28.5% improvement over the second-best performing YOLOv7 model. Despite these advancements, the generalizability of SRNet-YOLO to insect farming environments remains uncertain, as the dataset used for model evaluation did not account for overlapping instances or the higher insect densities typically observed in insect farming settings.

1.2 Motivation and Contributions of This Study

Mass insect rearing for protein production presents a viable alternative to conventional animal feeds such as soybean and fishmeal. However, automation is crucial for reducing costs, enhancing yield, and ensuring consistent quality and quantity. While recent research has explored machine vision-based solutions for insect detection and counting (Hansen et al., 2022; Majewski et al., 2022; Papadopoulos et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024), these efforts have largely relied on size-limited and non-public datasets. Given that machine vision models require large amounts of data to achieve high performance, the development and public release of a comprehensive dataset are essential. Publicly available datasets would enable benchmarking and comparison across different models and approaches, driving further advancements in automated insect farming.

This paper introduces a synthetic dataset for mealworm beetle detection, designed to facilitate model training and evaluation. Initial experiments establish a baseline for performance, after which the model is retrained on a significantly smaller real-world farm dataset to assess its ability to generalise. The following section details the dataset preparation process and the methodologies employed for insect detection.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Data

2.1.1 Synthetic

Machine vision models require a lot of imagery data to train and test models. Papadopoulos et al. (2024) published a publicly available, fully annotated dataset for the detection and segmentation of *Tenebrio molitor*

larvae. However, no similar dataset for mealworm beetles is currently available in the public domain. For mass rearing, mealworms are kept in stacked trays where each tray has 5-7.5 cm of substrate. Each tray could have hundreds of beetles and manual labelling each instance of the beetle is a challenge. Therefore, a dataset was generated synthetically for the use case of mealworm farming. Additionally, the synthetic data were labelled automatically hence providing the opportunity to label 100+ images for training and testing models. Figure 1a was captured at a mealworm facility and was used as the background image. It shows the top view of the tray used for rearing mealworm beetles. The dimensions of the tray image are 4056×2970 px and the physical dimensions of the tray are 60×40 cm. Figure 1b shows the beetle image used for generating the synthetic dataset.

Figure 1: Images used to create synthetic dataset (a) Top view of tray used for rearing mealworm beetles (b) Adult mealworm beetle used to create synthetic dataset, Image from Flickr (Schmidt, 2017)

To account for the range of options in the actual scenario, randomness was included in terms of beetle position, direction, and total count. The position was randomized, and it was ensured that all beetles were distributed within the coordinates of the substrate. For direction, the beetle was ro-

tated randomly between 0-360 degrees. The total count was randomized from 50 to 1000 beetles in a single tray. Figure 2a shows an image from the synthetic dataset created containing 1000 beetles.

As the beetle count increases, the likelihood of overlapping and occlusion also rises, which may impair the model’s ability to accurately detect and count individual beetles, resulting in potential prediction errors. Therefore, for a comprehensive model evaluation based on beetle density, the synthetic dataset was categorized into four sets as shown in Table 1.

2.1.2 Real Farm

To evaluate the model’s performance in a real-world context, a small set of real-farm images was used for retraining and validation. The real farm image is shown in Figure 2b. Since the model was initially trained solely on a synthetic dataset, for retaining the model, only eight real farm images were selected—six for training and two for validation. This limited number of real-world images allowed for an assessment of how the model generalizes to actual farm conditions despite the primary reliance on synthetic data during training.

2.2 Methods

The You Only Look Once (YOLO) model was initially trained on a synthetically generated dataset. Furthermore, the model was retrained on a real farm dataset to evaluate its performance in a real-world scenario. The detection analysis was divided into several scenarios to determine the performance of the model for varying possibilities. The scenarios are shown in Table 2. The model was initially trained on whole images, since the images needed to be resized and downscaled to meet the computational requirements of the YOLO algorithm, the accuracy and performance of beetle detection were adversely impacted. This reduction in image resolution likely caused a loss of fine details, which are crucial for identifying features of the beetles. To enhance small object detection, approaches such as Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) (Lin et al., 2017) and Single Shot Multi-Box Detectors (SSD) (Liu et al., 2016) have been widely adopted. These models are particularly effective in scenarios where objects exhibit varying sizes, as they integrate multi-scale feature maps to improve detection performance across different object scales (Lin et al., 2017) (Liu et al.,

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Images used for analysis (a) Synthetically generated image with 1000 beetles in the tray (b) Real farm image

2016). However, in cases where the target objects, such as beetles, are small but of a relatively consistent size, the use of image patching presents a simpler and more effective solution. Therefore, the small object detection issue was addressed through the implementation of image patching techniques, a method that involves dividing an image into smaller sections or patches. Therefore, by dividing the image into smaller patches, the model was trained on the image patch, and its performance was compared. Furthermore, a sliding window mechanism was also considered as a post-processing step to avoid issues arising due to beetles lying on the border/edge of the patches.

The following is a brief description of the YOLO model, the pre- and post-processing mechanism used to improve model performance, and the performance metrics used for analysis.

2.2.1 YOLO

You Only Look Once (YOLO) is one of the state-of-the-art object detection models and is widely used due to its speed and accuracy (Zou et al., 2023). YOLO is one-stage proposal-free detection model, i.e. it predicts class probabilities and bounding box coordinates directly from the image in one pass and does not rely on proposal generators or refinement stages. It uses a single neural network for classification and bounding box prediction. Compared to two-stage detection models it provides better speed with a slight compromise on accuracy (Zou et al., 2023). Therefore, for the detection of adult mealworm beetles the YOLO model was examined. The model was first proposed in 2016 (Redmon et al., 2016) and since then further improvements to the model have been published. The PyTorch implementation of YOLOv8 was used for this analysis (Jocher et al., 2023).

2.2.2 Image Patching

To train the YOLO model for the whole image with default parameters, the image was resized to 640×640 px. Using higher image dimensions increased computational complexity, in our case resulting in out-of-memory errors. However, resizing images to a default size limits the accuracy of the model for the detection of smaller objects. Therefore, to avoid this downsizing issue and preserve model accuracy for small objects, an image patching mechanism was implemented. For 8×8 patching, the input image

Table 1: Dataset categories and naming

Dataset Category	Number of images	Number of beetles in single image	Dataset Label
Training Dataset 1	100	50-200	Train ₅₀₋₂₀₀
Training Dataset 2	100	500-1000	Train ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀
Testing Dataset 1	50	50-200	Test ₅₀₋₂₀₀
Testing Dataset 2	50	500-1000	Test ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀

Table 2: Scenarios to determine detection model performance for varying possibilities

Scenario	Model Training/Prediction	Label
1	Model trained on the whole image. Train ₅₀₋₂₀₀ dataset used for training with an 80:20 split.	WI ₅₀₋₂₀₀
2	Model trained on the whole image. Train ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀ dataset used for training with an 80:20 split.	WI ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀
3	Model trained on image patch by dividing the image into 8×8 patches (image divided into 8 horizontal and 8 vertical patches i.e., total 64 patches of single image). Train ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀ dataset used for training with an 80:20 split. The predicted results of the model was followed by NMS.	PI _{8x8}
4	Similar to Scenario 3 but image divided into 5×5 patches	PI _{5x5}
5	Model trained for PI _{8x8} and PI _{5x5} used but for prediction the predicted results of 8×8 and 5×5 were combined and followed by NMS.	PI _{8x8+5x5}
6	Model trained for PI _{8x8} used but for prediction sliding window mechanism was used with 50 percent overlap between adjacent patches i.e., instead of 8 horizontal and vertical patches each image had 15 horizontal and vertical patches. The prediction results of each patch was combined and followed by NMS.	PI _{8x8-slides}
7	Similar to scenario 6 but for 5×5 patches.	PI _{5x5-slides}

was divided into 8 horizontal and 8 vertical patches, resulting in 64 images of size 507×371 px each. Consequently, since the patch image size was less than 640×640 px, a size reduction was not applied to the image patch when using the default parameters for model training. However, this technique added overhead in prediction, as the input image was first divided into patches and model prediction was obtained for each patch and then the result of all patches was combined, followed by non-max suppression (NMS). For analysis, two different patching sizes were evaluated 8×8 and 5×5 . The beetles located at the boundary of the patch were distributed across two or more patches, resulting in portions of individual beetles being included in multiple patches. Consequently, the sliding window mechanism was also investigated to facilitate a comparison of the results.

2.2.3 Sliding Window

The sliding window approach is a post-training step. Instead of non-overlapping patches of image for prediction, 50% overlapped patches were used for prediction. For 8×8 image patches, this resulted in 15×15 patches.

The main purpose of using a 50% overlap in the sliding window approach was to address the issue of beetles lying on the boundaries of non-overlapping patches. In a vanilla non-overlapping patch-based approach, a beetle that was present on the edge of a patch might only be partially visible within multiple patches. This could lead to incomplete or inaccurate detection, as the model might not detect or detect partial parts of beetle. By introducing 50% overlapping between patches, the sliding window ensures that beetles at the boundaries of non-overlapping patches will also appear around the centre of the overlapping patch.

2.2.4 Non-Maximum Suppression

Non-maximum suppression (NMS) is a post-processing technique used in object detection models (Zou et al., 2023). It is mainly used to eliminate duplicate detections and identify the most relevant detected objects. For a given set of bounding boxes and associated confidence scores, the overlapping bounding boxes with a lower confidence score are discarded. The remaining boxes are the non-maximum suppression results. The NMS was used for post-processing patching and sliding-window approaches to reduce duplicate detections.

The detection analysis was divided into number of scenarios to determine model performance for varying possibilities. The scenarios are shown in Table 2.

2.2.5 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of object detection models is evaluated using various metrics (Padilla et al., 2021). In this paper, the model performance was evaluated based on the following metrics:

Precision is the ratio of correctly detected beetles to the total number of beetle detections.

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositives(TP)}{TruePositives(TP) + FalsePositives(FP)}$$

Recall is the ratio of the number of correctly detected beetles to the total number of beetles.

$$Recall = \frac{TruePositives(TP)}{TruePositives(TP) + FalseNegatives(FN)}$$

where True Positives (TP) are a count of correct detections of the beetles, False positives (FP) are a count of incorrect detection of a nonexistent beetle, and False negatives (FN) are a count of undetected beetles.

F1 Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

$$F1 = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Mean Average Precision (mAP) is a key metric used to evaluate the performance of object detection models. It combines precision and recall to provide a single measure of accuracy. The process involves calculating the Intersection over Union (IoU) for each predicted bounding box against the ground truth, plotting the precision-recall curve for each class, and then finding the area under the curve (Average Precision, or AP). The mAP is the mean of these AP values across all classes, offering a comprehensive assessment of the model’s ability to detect and accurately classify objects.

mAP⁵⁰ is a metric that evaluates the performance of object detection models at a fixed Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 0.50. It measures how well the model detects objects with at least 50% overlap between

the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes, focusing on easier detections. mAP^{50-95} provides a more comprehensive evaluation by averaging the mean average precision across multiple IoU thresholds, ranging from 0.50 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05. This metric captures the model’s performance across a wider range of detection difficulties, offering a thorough assessment of its accuracy and robustness.

The models were trained on Desktop PC with the following specifications: Processor: Intel(R) Core (TM) i9-10900F CPU @ 2.80GHz, RAM: 32.0 GB, GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 (10 GB Dedicated memory).

3 Results

Initially, the models were trained and tested on synthetically generated dataset as this offered flexibility for analysis for varied counts of beetles in the labelled dataset. Therefore, the analysis for the synthetic dataset was crucial for creating a labelled real dataset. As shown in Table 1 the training and testing dataset contained two varying ranges of beetles i.e. 50-200 and 500-1000, representing varying levels of complexity and density. The YOLO model was first trained on Train_{50-200} (WI_{50-200} , Scenario 1 in Table 2), where the idea was to evaluate model performance with similar-count beetle images (Test_{50-200}) and with increased beetle count ($\text{Test}_{500-1000}$). Analysing the model’s performance in both test scenarios was essential for labelling the real dataset. If the model performs well in both cases, the effort required for labelling the real dataset can be significantly reduced by focusing on images with fewer counts. Furthermore, the model was also trained on $\text{Train}_{500-1000}$ dataset ($\text{WI}_{500-1000}$, Scenario 2 in Table 2). This was particularly important for understanding how well the model performs in more challenging scenarios with increased density. For image patch models, each image of the $\text{Train}_{500-1000}$ dataset was divided into 8×8 and 5×5 patches, this approach was aimed to improve detection accuracy as image will not be downscaled by YOLO. Both training datasets had 100 images with an 80:20 split for training and validation. The models performance for validation is summarized in Table 3. In the case of the WI_{50-200} model, the mAP^{50} was 98% but it degrades to around 80% for mAP^{50-95} . This clearly indicates though the model was able to detect beetles but it was failing to mark the exact location of the beetles. Similar behaviour was observed for $\text{WI}_{500-1000}$ but the loss in per-

formance was even more significant due to the increased number of beetles in the dataset. However, the image-patching mechanism demonstrated its superiority as there was no difference in mAP value (around 99%) even when the IoU threshold was increased. Additionally, the precision and recall values for all models show that more than 90% detections of the beetle instances were correctly predicted, especially for image patch models the accuracy was more than 98%. Hence, the patch-based models, outperformed the whole-image models in all key metrics, demonstrating higher accuracy, consistency, and a better balance between Precision and Recall. These findings suggest that using smaller image patches improves object detection performance, making it a more effective approach for this task. All models (Table 2) were also retrained with a limited real dataset. The total number of images used for training and validation was eight with a 75:25 split. The models performance for validation is summarized in Table 4.

For the WI_{50-200} model, the mAP^{50} was 92% but this value declined substantially to around 56% for mAP^{50-95} . This observation highlighted that, while the model effectively detected the presence of beetles, it struggled to accurately localize their exact positions. A similar pattern was observed for $WI_{500-1000}$; however, the performance degradation was even more pronounced due to the increased number of beetles in the dataset. Though image patch models also show a significant decrease in mAP^{50-95} values but still outperform the whole-image trained models. Additionally, the precision, recall and F1 score for image patch models show that more than 90% of detections of the beetle instances were correctly predicted. Overall, the results highlight the effectiveness of using image-patches for beetle detection, although real-world data presented some performance challenges not observed in the synthetic dataset. Despite these challenges, the image-patch based models continued to show significantly better accuracy compared to the whole-image models.

To further evaluate model performance the models predictions were visually observed for $Test_{50-200}$, $Test_{500-1000}$ and real datasets.

3.1 $Test_{50-200}$ dataset

Figure 3a-3g show model prediction for image from the $Test_{50-200}$ dataset for WI_{50-200} , $WI_{500-1000}$, PI_{8x8} , PI_{5x5} , $PI_{8x8+5x5}$, $PI_{8x8-slider}$ and $PI_{5x5-slider}$ respectively.

Figure 3: Model predictions for the image from Test_{50-200} dataset, the missed detections are marked with a yellow circle and false detections are marked with a blue circle. (a) WI_{50-200} model (b) $\text{WI}_{500-1000}$ model (c) PI_{8x8} model (d) PI_{5x5} model (e) $\text{PI}_{8x8+5x5}$ model (f) $\text{PI}_{8x8\text{-slider}}$ model (g) $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$ model

For Test_{50–200} dataset, the WI_{50–200} model (Figure 3a) showed some limitations, particularly in detecting beetles that were overlapping, leading to a few missed detections. On the other hand, the WI_{500–1000} model (Figure 3b) had significant issues, including missing many beetles and generating numerous false positives. The models based on image patches, PI_{8x8} and PI_{5x5} (Figure 3c and 3d), had the highest number of false detections. This was caused by the way the predictions were made using small patches of the image. Beetles located near the edges of these patches were detected in multiple patches, which resulted in duplicate detections. Although Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) was applied to remove redundant detections, it failed to eliminate these duplicates because the predicted bounding boxes did not overlap. This highlights a limitation in the use of small image patches for prediction tasks.

Since the image-patch models provide better detection accuracy but with the problem of lot of duplicate detections, two separate solutions, dual image patch models and a sliding window mechanism were evaluated. As explained in the methods section, for dual image-patch models, the prediction results of PI_{8x8} and PI_{5x5} were combined and then followed by NMS to remove duplicate detections. Whereas in the case of the sliding mechanism, a sliding-window based approach was used for predicting detections in each patch.

Compared to the PI_{8x8} model, the dual image patch (Figure 3e) showed better predictions as it had removed false detections. However, in comparison with PI_{5x5}, though the dual image-patch approach removed false detections, the number of missed detections had increased too. The prediction results for the sliding-window based approach are shown in Figure 3f and 3g for 8×8 and 5×5 , respectively. Due to the 50% overlap between patches in sliding-window, false detections occurring at the edges of patches are positioned in the center of the overlapping patch. Consequently, beetles located within this overlapping area are detected. The application of Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) ensures that redundant non-overlapping bounding boxes are eliminated, thereby refining the detection results. Therefore, the sliding-window approach showed superior detection results by reducing false detections.

3.2 Test_{500–1000} dataset

The model predictions for image from the Test_{500–1000} dataset are shown in Figure 4a-4g for WI_{50–200}, WI_{500–1000}, PI_{8x8}, PI_{5x5}, PI_{8x8+5x5}, PI_{8x8–slider} and PI_{5x5–slider} respectively.

For Test_{500–1000} dataset, the performance of the WI_{50–200} model (Figure 4a) was significantly reduced in this test because it was trained specifically on the Train_{50–200} dataset. As a result, the model failed to accurately detect many overlapping or closely located beetles. In comparison, the WI_{500–1000} model (Figure 4b) performed better, as it was trained on the Train_{500–1000} dataset; however, it still exhibited a high number of false and missed detections. Similar to the results observed for the Test_{50–200} dataset, the image patch models, PI_{8x8} and PI_{5x5} (Figure 4c and 4d), produced a large number of false detections. The dual image-patch approach (PI_{8x8+5x5}) (Figure 4e) also did not yield significant improvements over these models. In contrast, the models incorporating post-processing with the sliding-window method (PI_{8x8–slider} and PI_{5x5–slider}) (Figure 4f and 4g) showed improved prediction performance. Among these, the PI_{5x5–slider} model demonstrated the most notable enhancement. The prediction results for the best-performing PI_{5x5–slider} model are shown in Figure 4g.

3.3 Real-world data

The models were also evaluated for images from mealworm beetle farm. Figure 5a-5g show the model predictions for image from real data by WI_{50–200}, WI_{500–1000}, PI_{8x8}, PI_{5x5}, PI_{8x8+5x5}, PI_{8x8–slider} and PI_{5x5–slider} respectively. The test image contained approximately 134 beetles, a count similar to the dataset on which the WI_{50–200} model was trained. As a result, the WI_{50–200} model (Figure 5a) accurately predicted 98 beetles but struggled with detecting those that were closely located. In contrast, the WI_{500–1000} model (Figure 5b) performed poorly, predicting only 56 beetles and failing to identify many, even in non-overlapping open spaces. The image-patch models (PI_{8x8} and PI_{5x5}) (Figure 5c and 5d) predicted approximately 135 instances, but their performance was affected by inaccuracies in bounding box placement. Additionally, some beetles were missed, and those positioned on patch boundaries were detected multiple times, leading to duplicate detections.

The PI_{8x8+5x5} model prediction is shown in Figure 5e. The sliding window

Figure 4: Model predictions for the image from $\text{Test}_{500-1000}$ dataset, the missed detections are marked with a yellow circle and false detections are marked with a blue circle. (a) WI_{50-200} model (b) $\text{WI}_{500-1000}$ model (c) PI_{8x8} model (d) PI_{5x5} model (e) $\text{PI}_{8x8+5x5}$ model (f) $\text{PI}_{8x8\text{-}slider}$ model (g) $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-}slider}$ model

models ($\text{PI}_{8x8\text{-slider}}$ and $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$) (Figure 5f and 5g) show prediction with very high accuracy. Since the $\text{PI}_{8x8+5x5}$, $\text{PI}_{8x8\text{-slider}}$ and $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$ models involved post processing therefore the evaluation metrics for these models for test image from real dataset are compiled in Table 5. The $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$ model showing the best performance as it had only 2 false detections and 3 missed detections. Therefore, resulting in an F1 score of 0.98.

The sliding window-based approach demonstrated significant improvement over both whole-image and image-patch techniques across all test scenarios, providing a more effective solution for beetle detection. Models such as $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$, in particular, exhibited higher accuracy, fewer false detections, and improved overall performance, making this method a more reliable and efficient choice for the beetle detection task.

3.4 Creating Segmentation Dataset

The analysis of beetle detection revealed that the YOLO model, combined with image-patching and sliding-window mechanisms, can achieve exceptional accuracy in detecting mealworm beetles. This outcome is particularly significant for applications in automated and remote monitoring systems, where precise detection and counting of beetles are essential. The highly accurate detection of beetles offers a practical solution to reduce the manual labelling effort required for segmentation tasks, by leveraging detection bounding boxes as prompts, this approach facilitates the effective use of segmentation models, such as Segment Anything (Kirillov et al., 2023).

To illustrate this capability, Figure 6a demonstrates the predictions of the Segment Anything model on a test image without the use of detection bounding boxes as prompts. The results clearly indicate that the model struggled to detect a significant number of beetles, leading to incomplete and unreliable mask predictions. However, when the same segmentation model was provided with bounding boxes generated by the best performing $\text{PI}_{5x5\text{-slider}}$ model, as shown in Figure 6b, the predictions improved dramatically, highlighting the efficacy of using detection outputs as prompts for segmentation. This finding underscores the critical role that an accurate detection model can play in enabling more sophisticated machine vision tasks.

Furthermore, the trained beetle detection model can serve as a foundational tool for creating high-quality datasets tailored to the segmentation

Table 3: Model performance evaluation metrics for synthetic dataset

Model	mAP ⁵⁰	mAP ⁵⁰⁻⁹⁵	Precision	Recall	F1
WI ₅₀₋₂₀₀	0.980	0.794	0.977	0.955	0.966
WI ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀	0.954	0.658	0.940	0.900	0.920
PI _{8x8}	0.991	0.990	0.995	0.982	0.989
PI _{5x5}	0.992	0.990	0.996	0.984	0.990

Table 4: Model performance evaluation metrics for real dataset

Model	mAP ⁵⁰	mAP ⁵⁰⁻⁹⁵	Precision	Recall	F1
WI ₅₀₋₂₀₀	0.922	0.560	0.883	0.879	0.881
WI ₅₀₀₋₁₀₀₀	0.823	0.406	0.798	0.739	0.767
PI _{8x8}	0.962	0.704	0.944	0.917	0.930
PI _{5x5}	0.979	0.700	0.948	0.934	0.941

Table 5: Model performance evaluation metrics for test image from real dataset

Model	Predicted (TP + FP)	False Detections (FP)	Missed Detections (FN)	Precision	Recall	F1
PI _{8x8+5x5}	141	9	2	0.94	0.98	0.96
PI _{8x8-slider}	143	10	1	0.93	0.99	0.96
PI _{5x5-slider}	133	2	3	0.98	0.98	0.98

Figure 5: Model predictions for the test image from real farm dataset, the missed detections are marked with a yellow circle and false detections are marked with a blue circle. (a) WI_{50-200} model (b) $WI_{500-1000}$ model (c) PI_{8x8} model (d) PI_{5x5} model (e) $PI_{8x8+5x5}$ model (f) $PI_{8x8-slider}$ model (g) $PI_{5x5-slider}$ model

Figure 6: Segment Anything model prediction (a) without bounding box prompt (b) with bounding box prompt

of beetles. Such datasets are invaluable for training advanced models for various downstream tasks, including size-based classification and anomaly detection.

4 Discussion

The analysis revealed that a model trained on whole images containing a lower number of beetles performed poorly when tested on images with a higher density of beetles or overlapping instances. Conversely, a model trained on whole images with a higher beetle count produced a significant number of incorrect predictions. This performance decline can be attributed to the high-resolution nature of the images (4056×2970 px), which are downscaled to 640×640 px during model training. As a result, the model struggles to retain essential beetle features, leading to reduced accuracy. Image patching offered a viable solution to this issue, as it minimized or eliminated the need for downscaling, thereby preserving beetle feature information. Additionally, the patching approach ensured that the model was exposed to diverse scenarios, including patches with no beetles and patches with a high beetle density, leading to better generalization. However, a limitation of simple patching as a preprocessing step was that beetles located at the boundaries of patches were not fully detected, resulting in multiple non-overlapping bounding boxes for the same beetle. This issue was addressed through a post-processing step using a sliding window

mechanism, where the model, trained on image patches, was provided with additional patches featuring 50% overlap. This overlapping approach ensured the correct detection of beetles situated at patch boundaries. Furthermore, Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) eliminated any duplicate non-overlapping bounding boxes from the initial patching process, as these overlap with the more accurate bounding boxes obtained from the overlapping patches. Overall, the sliding window mechanism demonstrated the highest performance among all evaluated approaches.

The beetle detection method provides a clear advantage over simple counting, as it allows the creation of an instance segmentation dataset, as shown in the Results section. This type of dataset makes it possible to classify beetles based on their size and to extract individual beetles for further analysis. Such detailed information can be useful for detecting anomalies as well. Overall, this approach supports more advanced and flexible analyses compared to basic counting methods.

5 Conclusion

A comprehensive evaluation was conducted on a state-of-the-art YOLO detection model to assess its effectiveness in the detection and counting of mealworm beetles, a task of significant importance in automated insect monitoring systems. This study addressed key challenges in beetle detection, including variability in density and distribution, by exploring methodological enhancements to the standard YOLO model. Specifically, the research investigated the application of image patching and sliding window mechanisms, which demonstrated substantial improvements in detection accuracy compared to the vanilla approach of training and predicting on whole images. These enhancements underscore the importance of innovative pre and post-processing techniques in improving object detection performance for tasks involving small or densely packed objects, such as beetles.

The models were rigorously trained and tested using both synthetic and real-world beetle datasets, ensuring their generalizability and robustness. To capture the challenges of beetle detection, various experimental scenarios were designed, and the models were analysed. Among the tested approaches, the $PI_{5x5-slides}$ model exhibited exceptional performance, achieving an F1 score of 98%, which highlights its ability to deliver precise and

reliable detection results. This level of accuracy not only demonstrates the efficacy of the post-processing sliding mechanism but also sets a new benchmark for beetle detection tasks.

Moreover, the study highlights the broader implications of these results beyond simple detection and counting. The highly accurate detection achieved by the proposed methodology serves as a critical preparatory step for downstream machine vision tasks, such as beetle segmentation, which require precise localization. Hence, demonstrating a clear pathway toward enhanced data preparation for advanced machine vision tasks, this work provides a novel and impactful contribution to the domain of insect monitoring and machine learning-based object detection.

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